

Examining the Impact of HR Practices on Employee Commitment in Hybrid Work Environments: An Empirical Study in the IT Industry

Shamitha P¹, J Ashwin Kumar²

¹MBA Student, School of Management Studies, Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai

²Assistant Professor, School of Management Studies, Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai

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Abstract: In recent years, hybrid work has become a widely used practice in the IT industry, transforming the way organizations manage their workforce. In such flexible work environments, HR practices play a crucial role in sustaining employee commitment. This study aims to examine the impact of HR practices on employee commitment in hybrid work environments. A quantitative research approach was used, and primary data were collected from 150 IT employees using a structured questionnaire. Secondary data were obtained from various journals, research articles, and other relevant academic sources to support the theoretical framework of the study. The data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel with the help of statistical tools such as percentage analysis and correlation analysis. The findings reveal that HR practices, including training, flexibility, performance appraisal, and communication, have a positive influence on employee commitment. The study concludes that effective HR strategies are essential for enhancing employee commitment in hybrid work models.

Keywords: HR Practices, Employee Commitment, Hybrid Work Environment, IT Industry, Work Flexibility, Organizational Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

The modern workplace has undergone a significant transformation with the adoption of hybrid work environments, especially after the global shift caused by digitalization and remote working trends. In the IT industry, employees are now working both remotely and from office locations, creating new challenges for organizations in managing human resources effectively. Employee commitment is a key factor that determines organizational success. Committed employees tend to be more productive, loyal, and engaged in their work. However, maintaining commitment in a hybrid work environment is difficult due to reduced face-to-face interaction, communication gaps, and lack of supervision. HR practices such as training and development, work flexibility, performance appraisal, and effective communication play a vital role in enhancing employee commitment. Therefore, this study focuses on examining how these HR practices influence employee commitment in hybrid work settings within the IT industry.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Human resource practices play a major role in shaping employee behavior and organizational outcomes. **David Guest (1997)** stated that effective HR practices improve employee commitment and organizational performance. Similarly, **Mark A. Huselid (1995)** found that strong HR systems lead to better employee productivity and lower turnover. This model includes affective, continuance, and normative commitment, which explain different ways employees stay connected to their organization. **Jeffrey Pfeffer (1998)** emphasized that HR practices such as training, employee involvement, and job security increase employee commitment. In addition, **Alan M. Saks (2006)** explained that HR practices improve employee

engagement, which leads to higher commitment. With the rise of remote and hybrid work, new factors have emerged. **Ravi S. Gajendran and David A. Harrison (2007)** found that flexible work arrangements improve job satisfaction and commitment. Similarly, **Tammy D. Allen et al. (2015)** highlighted that flexibility reduces stress and improves employee engagement. Recent studies such as **Kevin M. Kniffin and Bin Wang et al. (2021)** show that communication, support, and autonomy are important factors in maintaining employee commitment in hybrid work environments. However, there is limited research focusing specifically on the IT industry in hybrid work settings, which creates a gap that this study aims to address.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY: To examine the impact of HR practices on employee commitment in hybrid work environments in the IT industry.

This study uses a quantitative research approach to examine the relationship between HR practices and employee commitment in hybrid work environments within the IT industry. A survey method was employed to collect data from employees working under hybrid work models. Both primary and secondary data sources were used for the study. Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to IT employees, and responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 represents Strongly Agree to 5 represents Strongly Disagree, to assess HR practices and employee commitment. Secondary data were obtained from various journals, research articles, and other relevant academic sources to support the theoretical framework of the study. The sample size is 150 employees was selected using the convenience sampling technique, based on accessibility and willingness to participate. For data analysis, statistical tools such as percentage analysis and correlation analysis were applied using Microsoft Excel to examine the relationship between HR practices and employee commitment.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

TABLE 1.1: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE	OPTIONS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
GENDER	Male	93	62
	Female	57	38
	TOTAL	150	100
AGE	Below 25	39	26
	25 - 35	56	37
	36 - 45	36	24
	Above 45	19	13
	TOTAL	150	100
WORK EXPERIENCE	Less than 2 years	37	25
	2 - 5 years	59	39
	5 - 10 years	34	23
	Above 10 years	20	13
	TOTAL	150	100
JOB ROLE	Developer	64	43
	Manager	37	25
	Analyst	31	21
	Other	18	12
	TOTAL	150	100
WORK MODE	Remote	39	26
	Work from Office	44	29
	Hybrid	67	45
	TOTAL	150	100

Source: Primary Data

The percentage analysis was used to understand the demographic profile of the respondents. The results show that a majority of the respondents belong to the age group of 25–35 years, indicating that most employees in the IT industry are young and active professionals. In terms of gender, both male and female respondents are represented, showing a balanced participation in the study. With respect to work experience, most respondents have 2–5 years of experience, which indicates that the

sample mainly consists of early-stage professionals. Regarding job roles, employees from different positions such as developers, managers, and analysts have participated, providing a diverse perspective. It is also observed that a large number of respondents are working in a hybrid mode, which supports the relevance of the study. Overall, the percentage analysis clearly shows that the data collected is suitable for analyzing HR practices and employee commitment in hybrid work environments.

TABLE 1.2: CORRELATION ANALYSIS RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WORK FLEXIBILITY AND EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT IN HYBRID WORK ENVIRONMENTS

	The organization offers flexibility in work schedules	I am willing to put extra effort to support my organization in a hybrid work setting
The organization offers flexibility in work schedules	1	
I am willing to put extra effort to support my organization in a hybrid work setting	0.9907	1

Source: Primary Data

Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between work flexibility and employee commitment in hybrid work environments. The results indicate that there is a positive relationship between the variables. This means that when the organization provides more flexibility in work schedules, employees are more willing to put extra effort to support the organization. The positive correlation suggests that flexibility is an important HR practice that influences employee behavior. Employees who experience flexible work arrangements tend to feel more motivated and are willing to contribute more towards organizational goals. Overall, the findings show that work flexibility plays a significant role in improving employee commitment in hybrid work environments in the IT industry.

5. FINDINGS

The findings of the study reveal that the majority of respondents belong to the age group of 25–35 years, indicating that most employees in the IT industry are young professionals. Both male and female employees have participated in the study, showing a balanced representation. It is also observed that most respondents have 2–5 years of work experience, which suggests that the sample mainly consists of early-stage professionals. A large number of respondents are working in a hybrid work environment, supporting the relevance of the study. The results further indicate that employees generally agree that HR practices such as training, flexibility, performance appraisal, feedback, and communication are effectively implemented in their organizations. The correlation analysis shows a positive relationship between work flexibility and employee commitment, indicating that employees who experience flexibility in work schedules are more willing to put extra effort to support their organization. Overall, the findings suggest that HR practices play an important role in enhancing employee commitment in hybrid work environments in the IT industry.

6. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that HR practices play an important role in influencing employee commitment in hybrid work environments in the IT industry. From the results, it is clear that when organizations provide good HR practices such as flexibility, training, performance appraisal, feedback, and proper communication, employees feel more motivated and committed towards their work. In particular, flexibility in work schedules helps employees to balance their work and personal life, which makes them more willing to put extra effort for the organization. The study also shows that in hybrid work settings, employees expect support from the organization to maintain their level of commitment. Therefore, organizations should focus on improving their HR practices according to the changing work environment. Overall, better HR practices lead to higher employee commitment and help the organization to achieve its goals successfully.

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